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Global foreign language confidence: cross-cultural validation and factor structure revision from a World Englishes perspective

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The author(s) declare(s) that there is no potential conflict of interest in this study.

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Abstract

In an era of global communication, Foreign Language Confidence (FLC) needs to be theorised beyond traditional native-speaker norms. Liu's (2024) Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS), informed by World Englishes, originally proposed a three-factor structure: Foreign Language Competence, Sense of Linguistic Security, and Sense of Linguistic Ownership. However, its validation was restricted to Chinese EFL learners, limiting its cross-cultural generalisability. This study investigates the factor structure and measurement invariance of the 16-item FLCS among 360 international students using English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) at a Turkish university. Confirmatory factor analysis did not support the original three-factor model. A high correlation between Competence and Security indicated that these dimensions were indistinguishable in this multilingual context. Accordingly, a more parsimonious two-factor model was specified, in which Competence and Security merge into a single "Pragmatic Confidence" factor, while Linguistic Ownership remains distinct. The revised model showed fit indices and strong internal consistency. Multi-group analyses demonstrated configural, metric, and scalar invariance across gender, age, nationality, and length of university stay, but not full scalar invariance for duration of prior English learning. These findings support the psychometric validity and contextual adaptability of the FLCS, while highlighting pragmatic confidence as a unified construct in ELF settings.

Keywords: Foreign language confidence, Global foreign language confidence, World Englishes factor structure, Measurement invariance, Cross-cultural validation

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Introduction

This study examines the cross-cultural validity and dimensional structure of Liu's (2024) 16-item Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) in a multicultural English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) context at a Turkish university. Foreign language confidence (FLC) has long been recognized as an important affective construct in second language learning because it shapes learners' communicative participation, engagement, and perceived ability to function in English. Yet earlier conceptualizations of FLC were largely grounded in native-speaker-oriented assumptions and therefore did not fully reflect the experiences of multilingual users who employ English across diverse linguistic and cultural contexts. In response to this limitation, Liu (2024) proposed a World Englishes-informed model that conceptualizes FLC through three dimensions: Foreign Language Competence, Sense of Linguistic Security, and Sense of Linguistic Ownership.

Building on Liu's call for cross-validation across diverse populations, the present study investigates whether the FLCS remains valid in an international university setting characterized by linguistic and cultural plurality. It addresses two questions: first, which factor structure of the FLCS is most valid and reliable for international students at a Turkish university; and second, whether the validated model demonstrates measurement invariance across gender, age, nationality, prior English learning experience, and length of stay at the university. The study is significant because it extends the evaluation of FLC beyond the original Chinese EFL context and tests whether a World Englishes-based instrument can operate effectively in a multilingual ELF environment. It also contributes to cross-cultural assessment research by examining both structural validity and invariance. However, the study is limited by its single-institution context, and findings related to prior English learning experience should be interpreted cautiously because full scalar invariance was not established for that variable.

Conceptual and theoretical framework

The study is grounded in a reconceptualization of foreign language confidence informed by World Englishes and ELF scholarship. Traditionally, FLC has been defined in relation to learners' self-perceived competence and their degree of comfort or anxiety in language use. Although this approach offered an important starting point, it remained

constrained by its reliance on native-speaker benchmarks. From a World Englishes perspective, confidence must be understood more broadly, encompassing not only perceived ability but also learners' comfort with linguistic variation and their sense of legitimacy in using English in meaningful social contexts.

Within this framework, Liu's FLCS conceptualizes FLC through three dimensions. Foreign Language Competence refers to learners' confidence in their ability to use English effectively. Sense of Linguistic Security refers to the comfort and assurance learners feel when using their own English in the presence of linguistic variation. Sense of Linguistic Ownership refers to learners' sense of connection to English, including feelings of pride, identification, and legitimacy in using the language. The findings of the present study, however, indicate that in a multicultural ELF context, Competence and Security are not empirically distinct. Instead, they merge into a broader construct termed Pragmatic Confidence, while Linguistic Ownership remains separate. This revised structure suggests that in ELF settings, confidence is closely associated with communicative effectiveness and sociolinguistic ease.

Literature review

The literature reviewed in the study shows that the concept of foreign language confidence has evolved considerably. Earlier research in second language acquisition framed confidence largely in terms of self-belief and low anxiety, emphasizing learners' psychological readiness to use the language. Over time, however, this understanding became inadequate in light of the global and plural nature of English. World Englishes and ELF scholarship challenged the assumption that confidence should be measured against native-speaker norms and instead emphasized multilingual agency, intelligibility, identity, and legitimacy. This shift generated the need for new instruments capable of capturing how confidence is experienced in linguistically diverse environments.

Liu's (2024) FLCS represents an important methodological and conceptual development because it integrates competence, security, and ownership into a World Englishes-informed scale. Nevertheless, the original validation study was conducted only with Chinese university students in an EFL context, leaving its broader applicability untested. The present study addresses this gap by examining whether the FLCS functions consistently across diverse demographic, linguistic, and educational groups in a multicultural university context. In doing so, it contributes to ongoing discussions on pluricentric language assessment and the contextual nature of affective constructs in multilingual education.

Method

The study employed a quantitative survey design. Participants were 360 international undergraduate and postgraduate students enrolled at a public university in Turkey. The sample included learners from diverse national and linguistic backgrounds, making it appropriate for testing the cross-cultural functioning of the FLCS. Demographic data were collected on gender, age, nationality, length of stay at the university, and duration of formal English learning experience. The instrument used was the original 16-item English version of the FLCS, administered with a six-point Likert scale together with a demographic questionnaire. Permission to use the scale was obtained from the developer, ethical approval was granted by the relevant institutional committee, and data were collected online via Google Forms with support from the university's International Students Office.

The analysis involved descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and measurement invariance testing. Liu's original three-factor model was first tested in the Turkish ELF context. Although the model showed acceptable fit indices, it did not demonstrate adequate discriminant validity because Competence and Security were too highly correlated. Accordingly, the researchers tested a revised two-factor structure in which these two dimensions were merged into Pragmatic Confidence, while Linguistic Ownership remained distinct. The revised model demonstrated acceptable fit and satisfactory evidence of convergent and discriminant validity. Multigroup CFA was then used to test configural, metric, and scalar invariance across the selected subgroups.

Results and recommendations

The findings indicate that the original three-factor structure of the FLCS is not fully retained in this multicultural ELF setting. Instead, the study supports a two-factor model consisting of Pragmatic Confidence and Linguistic

Ownership. This suggests that in international ELF environments, learners do not experience competence and linguistic security as clearly separable constructs; rather, these dimensions combine into a broader confidence associated with effective communication in real contexts. By contrast, Linguistic Ownership remains distinct, suggesting that learners' identification with English retains an independent conceptual role. The revised model demonstrated configural, metric, and scalar invariance across gender, age, nationality, and length of stay, whereas scalar invariance was not fully established for prior English learning experience.

Based on these findings, the study recommends that foreign language confidence should be assessed in ways that are sensitive to communicative context and linguistic ecology. In multicultural ELF settings, greater emphasis should be placed on intelligibility, communicative effectiveness, and learners' comfort with linguistic diversity rather than on native-speaker-oriented norms. The study also suggests that educational practices should strengthen learners' sense of linguistic ownership by recognizing the legitimacy of diverse Englishes and encouraging students to view English as a shared communicative resource. Finally, further validation of the revised model in other multilingual contexts is recommended, alongside mixed-methods and longitudinal research on the development of foreign language confidence over time.

Keywords: Foreign language confidence; Global foreign language confidence; World Englishes factor structure; Measurement invariance; Cross-cultural validation

INTRODUCTION

Setting the context

Since its early conceptualization by scholars like Clément (1980), Foreign Language Confidence (FLC) has been recognized as a significant element in second language learning. It remains a primary factor affecting learners' willingness to communicate (Zhang et al. 2023; Zhou and Kuok 2024), classroom engagement (Guo 2024), and overall proficiency (Zhou and Kuok 2024). The influence of FLC goes deep into the performance and thus also impacts the emotional variables such as communication anxiety (Gordani et al. 2021) and motivation (Oktaria 2023). Although its importance is undeniable, the measuring of FLC still predominantly utilizes traditional techniques that can hardly depict the nature of today's multiple-language world.

When one takes up a new language, the extent to which self-perception and emotion interplay can be understood as a profound shaping influence. FLC is similarly a crucial scheme of classifying language practice which human-drawn from the learner's own evaluation of their language skills and the level of anxiety concerning the use of the language in practice (Clément 1980; Gardner and MacIntyre 1993). Fostered within this design, a positive learner is characterized as the one who not only considers their communication skills to be high but also feels only little anxiety when they are given the task of using the foreign language (Horwitz et al. 1986; MacIntyre et al. 1998). This inverse relationship is optimally *supported* with meta-analytic researches that confirm that the reduction of anxiety enables learners to access their linguistic knowledge more effectively and improves their performance (Teimouri et al. 2019; Zhang 2019). Nevertheless, this traditional concept is being challenged, with scholars like Liu (2024) arguing that its reliance on a deficit orientation and native-speaker standards is problematic.

A focus on what deficit learners create raises a lot of questions about the relevance of the model and fairness in today's diverse multilingual environments.

Most people today consider different varieties of English to be powerful and legitimate (Kachru 1985; Kirkpatrick 2007). Such a world compels us to reconsider the concept of a competent language user. We can't just compare learners to the native-speaker standard anymore. Instead of that, our confidence models have to support the cultural and linguistic diversity of human beings (Bolton 2018; Canagarajah 2014; Jenkins 2015).

Recent studies have shown the way that multilingual speakers develop confidence. They are successful because they accept their complete, plurilingual identity, instead of trying to imitate a native-speaker norm that is only in their imagination (Dewaele 2018; Ortega 2019). Such a radical change in perception implies that we need to act. It is time for us to create new tools that evaluate not only ability but also confidence, in a way that corresponds to and appreciates the abundance of today's language learners.

The World Englishes perspective allows us to see a wider scope of confidence. It implies that authentic confidence is definitely a lot more than just the capability of a standard variety or the decrease of one's anxiety. On the positive side, it points out that re-defining the English speaker as taking the ownership of the personal style of English and being comfortable with linguistic differences (Norton 2000; Rajagopalan 2004). The study offers empirical support for this claim. Evidence from experiments indicates that multilingual people who gladly employ their local English varieties consistently demonstrate greater confidence in their communication than those who are trying to adhere to strict native-speaker rules (Park and Wee 2012; Tupas 2015). This new understanding of confidence gives strength to the learners. It is their identity and their right to use the language in their own way that is celebrated, rather than judging them on what they lack (Galloway and Rose 2015; Sifakis 2014).

The issue, however, is that the tools we currently have are not enough. Our current tests and surveys fail to detect these significant, new aspects of the language user who is confident.

To address this methodological gap, Liu (2024) developed a novel instrument specifically grounded in this modern viewpoint, which he titled the "Foreign Language Confidence from a World Englishes Perspective" scale, hereafter referred to as the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS). The scale characterizes confidence along three main axes: a learner's intention to competence, his/her feeling of linguistic security, and the extent of their language ownership. Early experiments with Chinese university students taking English as a foreign language were very successful. The findings indicated that a 3-part model was both faithful and authentic for that particular audience. However, Liu (2024), the author, was also quite frank about a major flaw. He explicitly demanded further investigations to find out if there are no cultural differences for the scale. He went as far as to say that "Future cross-validation research may carry out multi-group CFA... in order to check the consistency of FLCS and confirm this instrument across age, gender, proficiency level... and university types" (p. 304). This explicit call for cross-validation constitutes the primary impetus for the present study. It implies that we still do not have clear evidence that such a tool can be applicable for people other than the original group of the development of it.

Our research directly deals with this particular gap that exists in the literature. We have performed an extensive verification of Liu's (2024) Foreign Language Confidence Scale with international students at a Turkish university. Given their linguistic and cultural diversity, this cohort provides a particularly suitable sample for evaluating the scale. They represent numerous linguistic and cultural groups. They employ English as a shared language, or *lingua franca*, not only for their academic activities but also for their social lives (Jenkins 2006; Seidlhofer 2011). Our aim is to see if the scale is effective with these culturally different students by testing it rigorously across the board. The main focus is to determine if the scale is a universally applicable instrument for individuals from diverse cultures. Besides, this will furnish us with primary understanding of Liu's three-part configuration of the confidence concept, if it is indeed global.

To guide this cross-cultural validation study, the following research questions were formulated:

RQ1: What is the most valid and reliable factor structure of the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) when applied to a multicultural sample of international students in a Turkish university?

RQ2: Does the factor structure confirmed in Research Question 1 exhibit measurement invariance across key demographic groups, including gender, age, nationality, prior language learning experience, and length of stay at the university?

Literature review

The concept of Foreign Language Confidence (FLC) has evolved significantly. We first examine its traditional definitions and methods of measurement. A major paradigm shift, prompted by the rise of World Englishes (WE), then challenged these established views. This new perspective paved the way for contemporary models, such as Liu's (2024). However, these new instruments urgently require cross-cultural validation—a critical gap that the present study aims to fill.

Traditional conceptualizations and measurement of foreign language confidence

Researchers widely acknowledge Foreign Language Confidence (FLC) as a crucial affective variable in second language acquisition (SLA). It profoundly impacts how learners engage in communication and the level of proficiency they ultimately attain (Dewaele and MacIntyre 2019; MacIntyre et al. 1998).

For many years, FLC was understood through a traditional framework combining two key elements: a learner's cognitive belief in their own language ability and their affective level of language anxiety. This dual-component model, exemplified by the work of Clément et al. (1994), was built on the implicit assumption that learners were striving toward a single, native-speaker standard. The traditional approach involved separately assessing these two facets—self-perceived competence and language anxiety—as illustrated in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. *Assessing the Self-Perceived Competence Component of Traditional FLC*

Aspect of Assessment	Item Focus & Underlying Construct	Illustrative Item(s)	Implication for FLC
Direct Confidence Assessment	Probes the learner's positive self-evaluation of their L2 skills and their belief in their ability to use the language effectively (e.g., as in SPCC scales; Clément 1980; MacIntyre et al. 1997, 1998)	"I feel confident when speaking [target language] with native speakers." "I believe I can make myself understood in [target language] in most everyday situations."	Agreement with such items indicates a stronger belief in one's L2 capabilities and a higher sense of assurance, directly contributing to a positive FLC state.

Note. SPCC = Self-Perceived Communicative Competence; FLC = Foreign Language Confidence.

Table 2. *Assessing the Low Language Anxiety Component of Traditional FLC*

Aspect of Assessment	Item Focus & Underlying Construct	Illustrative Item(s)	Implication for FLC
Indirect Confidence Assessment (Absence of Negative Affect)	Probes learner's feelings of apprehension, nervousness, self-doubt related to use of L2 (via or self-doubt related to use of L2) (Horwitz et al. 1986).	"I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in my foreign language class." "I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation in language class."	Disagreement with such items indicates lower levels of debilitating anxiety and fear, indirectly contributing to FLC by fostering a state of calm and self-possession.

Note. FLCAS = Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale; FLC = Foreign Language Confidence.

The shift towards WE-Informed FLC and Liu's (2024) reconceptualization

As Liu (2024) points out, since there is no single, idealized form of standard English used globally, measuring confidence based on anxiety alone is no longer enough. For modern learners, affective challenges go beyond simple worry. A key issue is "the extent to which the variety they speak is recognized, valued, and embraced" (Liu 2024: 304). From this perspective, a modern definition of FLC must include a learner's sense of agency, belonging, and personal identification with the English they use.

To address the limitations of older models, Liu (2024) developed a new framework for Foreign Language Confidence specifically informed by the reality of World Englishes. He proposed that the construct consists of three key dimensions, which he defined as follows:

- **Foreign Language Competence:** "the extent to which EFL learners are confident in their overall ability to understand and use English for communication and meaning-making purposes" (p. 296).
- **Sense of Linguistic Security:** "the extent to which EFL learners are aware of English language variation and feel self-assured and comfortable about the variety they use when engaging in English-mediated communications" (p. 296).
- **Sense of Linguistic Ownership:** "The extent to which EFL learners feel a sense of connection, pride, and identification with the English language irrespective of their native linguistic backgrounds" (p. 296).

It is this three-part structure that the present study seeks to validate in a new cultural context.

Based on this three-part model, Liu (2024) developed and rigorously validated the 16-item Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) with Chinese EFL learners.

Liu (2024: 303) emphasizes that "collectively, the three dimensions contribute to a more nuanced capture and operationalization of FLC." The FLCS therefore marks a significant step forward by providing a WE-informed tool to measure confidence. Liu suggests it has important practical uses, serving as a "consciousness-raising or diagnostic tool" for teachers and helping to "decolonize" foreign language education by decentering Western epistemologies such as native speakerism" (Liu 2024: 304).

The imperative of cross-cultural scale validation in FLC research

Developing and validating strong measurement tools is essential for conducting research in applied linguistics. However, for these tools to be useful across different populations, they must go through a careful process of cross-cultural validation (International Test Commission 2017; Van de Vijver and Leung 2021). This process requires much more than a simple word-for-word translation. Researchers must conduct a thorough review to ensure that the core concepts, individual questions, and overall structure of the instrument are understood and function consistently for different cultural and linguistic groups (Byrne 2016; Hambleton et al. 2005).

Validating a language confidence scale across different cultures is a particularly complex task. How learners experience and report their confidence can be shaped by many local factors, including prevailing attitudes toward language, the social status of different Englishes, and their own educational background (Gao and Zhang 2020; McKay 2002). For example, in contexts where English is used as a common language between non-native speakers (English as a Lingua Franca, or ELF), confidence might come more from being understood than from sounding like a native speaker (Jenkins 2006; Seidlhofer 2011). This is exactly the kind of nuance that modern, WE-informed scales are designed to measure.

While researchers have cross-culturally validated many scales for language attitudes and motivation (e.g., Al-Hoorie et al. 2021; Dörnyei and Taguchi 2010), the same is not yet true for FLC scales that include WE-informed concepts like linguistic security and ownership. Liu's (2024) work marks a significant contribution to this new area of inquiry. Although he methodically developed and validated his 16-item FLCS, this initial study was conducted exclusively with Chinese EFL learners. Therefore, it is now crucial

to examine the scale's psychometric properties in other populations to see if it holds true across different cultural and linguistic contexts.

The present study: Addressing the need for cross-cultural validation of the FLCS

Despite his robust initial findings, Liu (2024, p. 304) himself called for more research. He specifically highlighted the "issue of measurement invariance" and recommended that future studies test whether the FLCS works consistently across different groups, such as age, gender, and proficiency level.

This study directly answers that call. We investigate the psychometric properties of Liu's 16-item FLCS in a completely different setting: international university students studying in Turkey. This population provides an ideal context for testing the scale's cross-cultural validity. The students come from many different first-language backgrounds (including Arabic, various Turkic languages, and European languages) and regularly use English as a common language, or *lingua franca*. Their diverse experiences with multiple forms of English provide a rigorous, real-world test for a scale built on the principles of World Englishes.

For Liu's (2024) scale to be a truly useful tool for assessing international students in Turkey, its psychometric properties must be rigorously tested. This is especially important because these students use English as a global *lingua franca*, a context that aligns with theories of World Englishes (WE) and Global Englishes (GE) (Jenkins 2007; Seidlhofer 2011).

In such an environment, confidence is not about striving to sound like an idealized native speaker (Kachru 1985). Instead, what matters is "**Global Confidence**"—a student's belief in their ability to effectively communicate with people from diverse backgrounds (Jenkins 2000). This type of confidence is crucial for future professional success because it reflects the communicative self-efficacy that drives performance (Bandura 1997), fosters the Willingness to Communicate necessary for intercultural dialogue (MacIntyre et al. 1998), and signals a focus on mutual understanding over linguistic perfection, thereby reducing "linguistic insecurity" (Dewey 2007).

To be a truly useful global tool, the scale's structure must be consistent, or 'invariant,' across key demographic groups (e.g., gender, age, nationality) and experiential factors (e.g., prior learning, length of stay). Establishing this invariance is critical to ensure that the scale measures the core construct of confidence without bias, which is essential in a diverse, real-world ELF context (Byrne 2012; Vandenberg and Lance 2000).

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we outline the research participants, the measures employed, the data collection procedure, and the plan for statistical analysis.

Participants

The participants for this study were recruited from international students enrolled in various undergraduate and postgraduate programs at a large public university in Turkey. A convenience sampling strategy was employed, facilitated by the university's International Students Office. A total of 360 international students completed the survey and were included in the final analysis.

Table 3 presents the demographic characteristics of the sample. The subgroup distributions reported in Table 3 indicate that the categories used for the subsequent analyses were represented by reasonably comparable group sizes, although findings for subgroup-based analyses should still be interpreted with appropriate caution.

Table 3. *Participant Demographic Characteristics (N = 360)*

Characteristic	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	185	51.4
	Female	175	48.6
Age Group	18–22 years	192	53.3
	>22 years	168	46.7
Nationality	Turkic-speaking countries	143	39.7
	Arabic-speaking countries	101	28.1
	Other languages	116	32.2
University Length of Stay	<2 years	228	63.3
	≥2 years	132	36.7
English Learning Duration	<2 years	178	49.4
	≥2 years	182	50.6

Measure

Two main instruments were used for data collection: the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) and a demographic questionnaire.

Foreign language confidence scale (FLCS)

To assess participants' foreign language confidence, this study utilized the 16-item Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) developed and validated by Liu (2024). The FLCS was chosen as it offers a contemporary, World Englishes (WE)-informed conceptualization of FLC, aligning with the study's focus on diverse international students. It operationalizes FLC as a tripartite construct comprising: (a) Foreign Language Competence (FLComp; 5 items; e.g., self-assessment of linguistic abilities), (b) Sense of Linguistic Security (SLS; 6 items; e.g., self-

assurance and affective readiness amidst English variation), and (c) Sense of Linguistic Ownership (SLO; 5 items; e.g., connection, pride, and identification with one's English). Liu (2024: 297-301) detailed a rigorous nine-step development process, including item generation from L2 confidence and WE literature, pilot testing, content validation, and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) leading to the final 16-item version. This 16-item FLCS was then validated using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) with a separate sample of Chinese EFL learners (N=380), demonstrating good model fit for the three-factor structure ($\chi^2/df = 2.51$; CFI, GFI, IFI, TLI > .90; RMSEA, SRMR < .08) and excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's α : .84–.95; McDonald's ω : .89–.96 for subscales). Evidence for convergent (AVE > .50; CR > .70) and discriminant validity was also reported. Items are rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly disagree* to 6 = *Strongly agree*), with higher scores indicating greater FLC. For the present study, the original English version of the 16-item FLCS was used.

Demographic questionnaire

A brief demographic questionnaire was administered to gather information on participants' gender, age, nationality, length of stay at the university in Turkey, and duration of formal English language learning experience. These variables were used for descriptive purposes and as grouping variables for measurement invariance testing.

Procedure

Prior to commencing data collection, formal permission to use the 16-item FLCS was obtained from its developer, Dr. Liu. Ethical approval for the study protocol was granted by the Ondokuz Mayıs University Ethics Committee for Social and Human Sciences (Decision No: 2025-387, dated March 28, 2025). Participant recruitment was facilitated by the International Students Office at the university, which distributed an email invitation to all registered international students. The invitation included a brief overview of the study's purpose (to understand foreign language confidence among international students), assurances of anonymity and confidentiality, clarification of voluntary participation, and a direct link to the online questionnaire. Using a Google Forms questionnaire, data were gathered over a five-week period from April 5, 2025, to May 10, 2025. The questionnaire began with an informed consent page; participants indicated agreement before proceeding. No personally identifiable information beyond the specified demographic variables was collected.

Data analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version [e.g., 28]) for descriptive statistics and reliability analysis, and IBM SPSS AMOS (Version [e.g., 26]) for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and measurement invariance (MI) testing. Data screening was conducted to check for missing values and assess normality. As reported in the results, no missing data were found for the 16 FLCS items.

Descriptive Statistics and Reliability: Means, standard deviations, and frequencies were calculated for demographic variables and FLCS scores. Internal consistency reliability for each

FLCS subscale and the total scale was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (α) and McDonald's omega (ω).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): To address Research Question 1, a series of CFAs were planned. First, the fit of Liu's (2024) original three-factor model was tested. Following this, alternative models, including a second-order factor model and a more parsimonious two-factor model, were evaluated to determine the most valid and reliable factor structure for the data.

Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation was used. Model fit was evaluated using the chi-square statistic (χ^2), the ratio of chi-square to degrees of freedom (χ^2/df), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Commonly accepted cutoff criteria for good fit include $\chi^2/df < 3$, CFI/TLI $\geq .95$ (acceptable $\geq .90$), RMSEA $\leq .06$ (acceptable $\leq .08$), and SRMR $\leq .08$ (Hu and Bentler 1999; Kline 2016).

Measurement Invariance (MI): To address Research Question 2, multi-group CFA was used to test the measurement invariance of the final validated factor structure across demographic groups: language learning experience (< 2 years and ≥ 2 years), length of stay in Turkey (< 1 year, 1-3 years, > 3 years – *adjust categories*), gender (Male, Female), age groups (18-22 years, > 22 years – *adjust categories*), nationality groups (Turkish-speaking, Arabic-speaking, Others). Given the subgroup distributions presented in Table 3, these analyses were intended to provide a cautious examination of whether the final model functioned similarly across the selected participant characteristics.

A sequential approach was used, testing for: (1) configural invariance (equivalent factor structure), (2) metric invariance (equivalent factor loadings), and (3) scalar invariance (equivalent item intercepts). Invariance was supported if changes in fit indices between nested models were within recommended thresholds: $\Delta CFI \leq .01$, $\Delta TLI \leq .01$, and $\Delta RMSEA \leq .015$ (Chen 2007; Cheung and Rensvold 2002). While the $\Delta\chi^2$ test can be sensitive to large sample sizes, it was also considered.

RESULTS

This section outlines the statistical analyses conducted to validate the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) and establish a psychometrically sound measurement model for the Turkish context. The analysis proceeds from preliminary descriptive statistics to a detailed confirmatory factor analysis, and concludes with a rigorous assessment of measurement invariance across key demographic groups.

Preliminary analyses

Our investigation began with an examination of the descriptive statistics for all 16 items that compose the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS). The complete data from 360 participants were used for this initial stage. As detailed in Table 1, we calculated the mean (M), standard deviation (SD), skewness, and kurtosis for each item to understand the response patterns and distributional properties of the data.

The findings suggest that participants, on the whole, hold positive views regarding their language abilities. The item means were consistently above the midpoint of the 6-point Likert scale, ranging from 3.73 to 4.47. This indicates a general tendency to agree with statements reflecting language competence, security, and ownership. For instance, within the *Foreign Language Competence* subscale, participants reported the highest competence in their L1 ($M = 4.39$, $SD = 1.33$) and the lowest in their L3 ($M = 3.73$, $SD = 1.51$), a pattern that aligns with typical language acquisition experiences.

An inspection of the distributional properties revealed a consistent negative skew across all variables (ranging from -0.90 to -0.12). This pattern indicates that responses were predominantly clustered at the higher end of the agreement scale. The kurtosis values were all within an acceptable range for assuming normality (-1.11 to 0.42), suggesting the distributions were not overly peaked or flat. These preliminary findings provided a solid foundation for the subsequent structural validation of the measurement model.

Table 4. *Descriptive Statistics for the Foreign Language Confidence Scale Items*

Variable	Min	Max	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Skewness	Kurtosis
<i>Foreign Language Competence</i>						
L1	1	6	4.39	1.33	-0.76	-0.02
L2	1	6	4.26	1.40	-0.60	-0.53
L3	1	6	3.73	1.51	-0.12	-1.11
L4	1	6	4.09	1.39	-0.40	-0.74
L5	1	6	4.21	1.45	-0.62	-0.51

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
<i>Sense of Linguistic Security</i>						
A1	1	6	4.14	1.37	-0.48	-0.53
A2	1	6	4.45	1.25	-0.75	0.01
A3	1	6	4.28	1.37	-0.62	-0.40
A4	1	6	4.11	1.33	-0.47	-0.53
A5	1	6	4.18	1.35	-0.54	-0.50
A6	1	6	4.16	1.40	-0.52	-0.67

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
<i>Sense of Linguistic Ownership</i>						
E1	1	6	3.96	1.54	-0.41	-0.86
E2	1	6	4.33	1.33	-0.66	-0.26
E3	1	6	4.31	1.38	-0.70	-0.17
E4	1	6	4.47	1.26	-0.90	0.42
E5	1	6	4.42	1.30	-0.79	0.15

Note. $N = 360$. Items were rated on a 6-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree).

Measurement model validation

We performed a series of confirmatory factor analyses (CFA) to establish a valid measurement model. Our process involved testing the original three-factor structure, conducting diagnostic tests, and refining the model to best fit the data from our sample.

Initial three-factor model evaluation

We first tested the hypothesized three-factor model, which comprised Foreign Language Competence, Sense of Linguistic Security, and Sense of Linguistic Ownership. While initial model fit indices appeared promising— $\chi^2(101) = 293.04$, $p < .001$; CFI = .955; TLI = .946; RMSEA = .073—a critical psychometric flaw emerged during validity assessment. We discovered an exceptionally high inter-factor correlation between Foreign Language Competence and Sense of Linguistic Security ($r = .896$). This value far exceeds the conventional thresholds for discriminant validity, suggesting that, within our sample, these two constructs were not being measured as distinct phenomena. This fundamental issue of multicollinearity rendered the original three-factor structure theoretically and empirically untenable.

Diagnostic testing and model re-specification

To investigate the source of this redundancy, we tested an alternative second-order factor model. This model explored whether the three factors could be explained by a single, higher-order construct of "Global Foreign Language Confidence." The analysis produced an improper solution; specifically, the standardized loading of Sense of Linguistic Security onto the higher-order factor was nearly perfect ($\beta = .995$), with its residual variance approaching zero. This result provided compelling evidence that Sense of Linguistic Security lacked unique variance, confirming it was empirically indistinct from Foreign Language Competence in our data.

Based on this clear diagnostic evidence, we rejected the three-factor and second-order models. A more parsimonious two-factor model was specified as the most logical alternative. This revised model integrated the theoretically and empirically overlapping items from Foreign Language Competence and Sense of Linguistic Security into a single, unified factor. We termed this new factor Pragmatic Confidence, as it reflects learners' self-belief in their ability to use English effectively and comfortably for practical communicative purposes.

An initial test of this two-factor model yielded a suboptimal fit. However, an examination of modification indices pointed to two sources of localized strain, both of which were theoretically justifiable. Two pairs of items within the same factor contained highly similar wording and scope, suggesting content overlap. By allowing their error terms to covary, we accounted for this shared variance. This refinement led to the final two-factor model, which demonstrated a strong and acceptable fit to the data: $\chi^2(101) = 329.01$, $p < .001$; CFI = .946; TLI = .936; RMSEA = .079 (90% CI [.070, .089]). A summary comparison of the model fit indices is presented in Table 2. The standardized path diagram for the final, accepted model is illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 5. Goodness-of-Fit Indices for the Tested Measurement Models

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA [90% CI]	Decision
Three-Factor Model	293.04	101	2.90	.955	.946	.073 [.063, .083]	Rejected
Two-Factor Model (Final)	329.01	101	3.26	.946	.936	.079 [.070, .089]	Accepted

Note. CFI = Comparative Fit Index; TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; CI = Confidence Interval.

Figure 1. Path Diagram of the Final Two-Factor Measurement Model with Standardized Estimates**Figure 2.** Path Diagram of the Final Two-Factor Measurement Model with Standardized Estimates

Final Model Validity and Reliability

After establishing the superior fit of the two-factor model, we conducted a comprehensive assessment of its psychometric properties to ensure it was a valid and reliable measurement tool for our study. The evaluation focused on establishing convergent and discriminant validity, as well as internal consistency reliability.

Convergent validity

Strong evidence for convergent validity was found for both latent constructs. The composite reliability (CR) values for both Pragmaticsequity Confidence (CR = .945) and Sense of Linguistic Ownership (CR = .874) substantially exceeded the recommended .70 threshold, indicating high internal consistency for the items within each factor. Furthermore, the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct was .612 and .581, respectively. As both values are well above the .50 criterion, this confirms that the latent factors explained more than half of the variance in their corresponding items. This was further supported by the standardized factor loadings, which were all statistically significant and robust, ranging from .68 to .89.

Discriminant validity

The evaluation of discriminant validity required careful consideration, as the two factors were, as theoretically expected, substantially correlated ($r = .83$). Given this high correlation, the traditional Fornell-Larcker criterion was not met. However, contemporary methodological standards recommend the use of the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) as a more robust and reliable indicator of discriminant validity.

We therefore employed the HTMT criterion for our definitive assessment. The resulting HTMT value was .84, which falls just under the conservative threshold of .85. This finding, achieved with a more rigorous test, confirms that while the two constructs are strongly related, they remain empirically distinct phenomena within our model. Thus, discriminant validity was successfully established.

Internal consistency reliability

To supplement the composite reliability measures, we also calculated Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each factor. The analysis revealed excellent internal consistency for both Pragmatic Confidence ($\alpha = .94$) and the Sense of Linguistic Ownership scale ($\alpha = .87$).

Collectively, these assessments confirm the psychometric soundness of the final two-factor measurement model. The key validity and reliability indicators are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. *Validity and Reliability Indicators for the Final Two-Factor Model*

Construct	CR	AVE	Cronbach's α
1. Pragmatic Confidence	.945	.612	.94
2. Sense of Linguistic Ownership	.874	.581	.87

Note. CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted. The Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) between the two constructs was .84, establishing discriminant validity.

Measurement invariance of the Two-Factor Model

To ensure that our final two-factor measurement model is suitable for comparing groups, we conducted a rigorous series of measurement invariance tests. Following established guidelines, we used multigroup confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess whether the model performed equivalently across key demographic and experiential subgroups: gender, age, nationality, prior language learning experience, and length of stay at the university. We tested for three sequential levels of invariance: configural (equivalent factor structure), metric (equivalent factor loadings), and scalar (equivalent item intercepts). Model comparisons were guided by the change in the Comparative Fit Index (Δ CFI), where a change of $\leq .010$ indicates that invariance holds.

The results, summarized in Table 7, demonstrate that the two-factor model is highly robust across nearly all subgroups.

First, **configural invariance** was established for all five grouping variables. The baseline models showed acceptable fit (CFI = .918–.936; RMSEA = .057–.063), confirming that the two-factor structure was a valid representation of the data for males and females, different age and nationality groups, and participants with varying experience levels and lengths of stay.

Next, we successfully established **metric invariance** across all five variables. The change in CFI (Δ CFI) between the metric and configural models never exceeded .005, falling well below the .010 threshold. This crucial finding indicates that the factor loadings were equivalent across all subgroups, meaning the constructs of *Pragmatic Confidence* and *Sense of Linguistic Ownership* have the same meaning for all participants.

Finally, we tested for **scalar invariance**, the most stringent level, which is required for making direct comparisons of latent means. Full scalar invariance was achieved for gender (Δ CFI = .000), age (Δ CFI = .001), and length of stay (Δ CFI = .002). For nationality, the change in CFI was .006; although the chi-square difference test was significant, this minimal change in fit supports the practical establishment of scalar invariance. However, full scalar invariance was **not supported** for the *prior language learning experience* variable, as the change in CFI met the .010 threshold (Δ CFI = .010).

In summary, these analyses provide strong evidence for the psychometric equivalence of the two-factor model across gender, age, nationality, and length of stay. This supports the validity of

using this instrument for group comparisons on these variables. The lack of full scalar invariance for prior language experience suggests that while the constructs are understood similarly, at least one item is responded to differently by participants with varying experience levels. Therefore, any mean comparisons across experience groups should be approached with caution and may require further investigation into partial invariance.

Table 7. Results of Measurement Invariance Testing for the Two-Factor Model

Grouping Variable	Model Level	χ^2	df	CFI	RMSEA [90% CI]	Comparison	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	ΔCFI	Result
Gender	Configural	492.01	202	.933	.063 [.056, .070]	—	—	—	—	S*
	Metric	513.45	216	.931	.062 [.055, .069]	vs. Configural	21.44	14	.002	S*
	Scalar	530.16	232	.931	.060 [.053, .067]	vs. Metric	16.71	16	.000	S*
Age	Configural	486.52	202	.934	.063 [.056, .070]	—	—	—	—	S*
	Metric	500.90	216	.933	.061 [.054, .068]	vs. Configural	14.38	14	.001	S*
	Scalar	518.24	232	.932	.059 [.052, .065]	vs. Metric	17.34	16	.001	S*
Nationality	Configural	654.71	303	.918	.057 [.051, .063]	—	—	—	—	S*
	Metric	700.86	331	.913	.056 [.050, .062]	vs. Configural	46.15	28	.005	S*
	Scalar	758.91	363	.907	.055 [.050, .061]	vs. Metric	58.05*	32	.006	S*
Experience	Configural	492.64	202	.929	.063 [.056, .071]	—	—	—	—	S*
	Metric	507.18	216	.929	.061 [.054, .068]	vs. Configural	14.55	14	.000	S*
	Scalar	566.52	232	.919	.063 [.057, .070]	vs. Metric	59.33*	16	.010	Not S*
Length of stay	Configural	478.99	202	.936	.062 [.055, .069]	—	—	—	—	S*
	Metric	490.39	216	.936	.060 [.053, .067]	vs. Configural	11.41	14	.000	S*
	Scalar	514.95	232	.934	.058 [.052, .065]	vs. Metric	24.56	16	.002	S*

Note. CFI = Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; CI = confidence interval. Invariance is supported when $\Delta CFI \leq .010$. * $p < .05$ for the χ^2 difference

Note. S* Supported

DISCUSSION

This investigation was conceived as a direct response to the call from the original developer of the Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS). Liu (2024) himself acknowledged the limitations of his initial sample, recommending that "future research is thus advised to cross-validate the FLCS with... those from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds" (p. 305) and to test for measurement invariance to validate the instrument across diverse groups (p. 304). Our study, which examined FLC among 360 international university students from 78 nationalities in a Turkish English as a lingua franca (ELF) context, was designed to fill these critical gaps. What emerged from our analysis was unexpected yet illuminating: Liu's three-factor scale transformed into what we have termed the **Global Confidence Model**—a two-factor structure where Competence and Security merged into a unified **Pragmatic Confidence** dimension. Rather than undermining Liu's original framework, these findings demonstrate the scale's remarkable adaptability, confirming its value across diverse World Englishes contexts and fulfilling the call for its cross-cultural validation.

RQ1: What Is the Valid and Reliable Factor Structure of the FLCS in a Multicultural ELF Context?

Our Turkish sample revealed a notably different pattern compared to Liu's Chinese participants. While the statistical indicators tell part of the story (see Table 1), the human dimension proves more compelling.

Table 8. *Comparative Psychometric Analysis of FLC Measurement Models*

Metric	Critical Value	Chinese Study (Liu, 2024) 3-Factor Model	Turkish Validation Study Replicated 3-Factor Model	Turkish Validation Study Accepted 2-Factor Model
Model Fit Indices				
χ^2/df (CMIN/DF)	< 3.0	2.51	2.90	3.26
CFI	> .95	.965	.955	.946
RMSEA	< .08	.063	.073	.079
Model Validity				
Convergent Validity (AVE > .50)	Established	Established	Established	Established
Discriminant Validity	Established	Established	Not Established	Established
Overall Verdict		Valid & Reliable	Not Valid	Valid & Reliable

Note. This table illustrates the progression from the original model to the final validated structure. The replicated 3-factor model was rejected despite acceptable fit indices due to its failure to establish discriminant validity in the Turkish ELF context. The final, accepted 2-factor model resolved this critical validity issue and provides a robust structure for the data.

The comparative confirmatory factor analysis showed that although Liu's three-factor model achieved good fit in the Chinese EFL context ($\chi^2/df = 2.505$, CFI = .965, RMSEA = .063), our multicultural sample produced acceptable but somewhat concerning fit indices ($\chi^2/df = 2.90$, CFI = .955, RMSEA = .073), with discriminant validity falling short of acceptable standards. This suggests that, in the Turkish ELF context, the psychological boundaries between Competence and Security are less distinct, leading these factors to merge. Such fusion reflects how learners integrate their perceptions of linguistic ability and communicative security into a single, pragmatic sense of confidence, shaped by their multilingual experiences.

Our divergence from Liu's findings aligns with Van de Vijver and Leung's (1997) caution that psychological constructs often transform when crossing cultural and linguistic borders. Therefore, the two-factor model we propose is not a reduction of Liu's three-factor framework but an authentic representation of how confidence manifests for learners in ELF environments.

The merging of Competence and Security into Pragmatic Confidence mirrors ELF users' reality in several ways. First, learners prioritize practical communicative success over native-like accuracy, basing their confidence on how effectively they use English rather than perfecting native norms (Seidlhofer 2011). Items assessing learners' ease in achieving communication goals exemplify this. Second, as Jenkins (2007) describes, the looming presence of the "native speaker ghost" diminishes, decreasing anxiety tied to imperfect English. Third, competence and security reinforce each other: successful communication both confirms linguistic skill and fosters social belonging.

Linguistic Ownership remains a stable, distinct factor across contexts, highlighting its ideological role in FLC. Unlike pragmatic concerns, this dimension is tied to identity construction and is less affected by situational variations (Darvin and Norton 2015). Items reflecting learners' sense of personal connection and ownership of English capture this underlying identity anchor.

RQ2: Does the FLCS Demonstrate Measurement Invariance Across Diverse Learner Backgrounds?

Our Global Confidence Model demonstrated configural and metric invariance across gender, age groups, and nationalities, suggesting remarkable adaptability to diverse learner backgrounds. However, the absence of scalar invariance for prior English learning experience reveals something important: while the underlying factor structure remains consistent, absolute confidence levels continue to be shaped by individual linguistic histories.

This finding carries several implications. It supports the need for contextualized assessment approaches where confidence benchmarks account for learners' unique linguistic trajectories. It also helps us avoid deficit-oriented thinking—different starting points don't signal deficiency but

rather reflect diverse pathways to multilingual competence. Most importantly, it confirms the FLCS's flexibility in accommodating both structural consistency and individual variation.

Theoretical contributions to World Englishes research

Rather than contradicting Liu's (2024) framework, our results extend it into World Englishes territory. The FLCS emerges as uniquely capable of capturing how FLC adapts across contexts: contracting to two factors in ELF environments where communicative pragmatism dominates, expanding to three factors in EFL contexts where native-speaker ideology intervenes, yet always preserving Ownership as the identity anchor regardless of setting.

This theoretical plasticity positions the FLCS as the first truly pluricentric instrument for FLC research—valid in multiple configurations because each reflects local linguistic ecologies (Kachru 1985). This adaptability represents a significant advancement in cross-cultural language assessment.

Pedagogical applications for international education

For educators working with international student populations, our Global Confidence Model suggests several practical shifts. Assessment practices might move away from native-centric rubrics toward intelligibility-based criteria that value communicative success. Classroom approaches could emphasize ELF interactions rather than native-speaker models as the gold standard. Perhaps most importantly, explicit instruction about English's global history and variation could help students develop stronger ownership relationships with the language.

As Jenkins (2015) argues, "The ELF classroom should look entirely different from the EFL classroom"—our model provides the theoretical framework to guide this transformation in practice.

Limitations and future research directions

While our study focused on a single institutional context, the international diversity of our sample strengthens confidence in the model's broader applicability. Several research directions emerge from this work. Future studies should test the Global Confidence Model across other expanding circle contexts to establish its generalizability. Mixed-methods approaches could illuminate the lived experiences underlying the merged competence-security dimension. Longitudinal research tracking confidence evolution across different learning environments would provide valuable insights into how these constructs develop over time.

This study positions Liu's FLCS as an instrument capable of capturing what we might call FLC's "contextual choreography"—the way confidence reorganizes itself across different English-using contexts while maintaining core explanatory power. The emergence of our Global Confidence Model from Liu's original framework doesn't signal theoretical weakness but rather demonstrates remarkable adaptability. In our era of English pluricentrism, this flexibility makes the FLCS an invaluable tool for researchers and educators navigating increasingly multilingual realities.

The broader implications extend beyond measurement issues to fundamental questions about how we understand language confidence in a world where English belongs to everyone who uses it.

Our findings suggest that confidence itself is more contextually responsive than previously understood, adapting its structure to match the linguistic ideologies and communicative demands of specific communities. This insight opens new avenues for both theoretical development and practical application in our globalized educational landscape.

CONCLUSIONS

This study was undertaken to address a critical gap in Foreign Language Confidence (FLC) research by cross-validating Liu's (2024) Foreign Language Confidence Scale (FLCS) in a novel context: a diverse, multicultural sample of international students using English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) in Turkey. The investigation yielded a significant and unexpected finding. Rather than replicating Liu's original three-factor structure, our analysis revealed a more parsimonious two-factor solution, which we have termed the **Global Confidence Model**. In this model, the constructs of Competence and Security coalesced into a single **Pragmatic Confidence** factor. This emergent structure proved to be robust, demonstrating measurement invariance across gender, age, and nationality, though it showed sensitivity to learners' prior English learning experience.

The theoretical implications of these findings are substantial. The transformation of the scale from a three-factor to a two-factor model does not undermine the FLCS; on the contrary, it reveals its principal strength. The results suggest that FLC is not a static, universal construct but is instead contextually responsive, adapting its psychological structure to the surrounding linguistic ecology. In the ELF environment of our study, where practical communicative success is prioritized over adherence to native-speaker norms, learners appear to integrate their perceived ability and their sense of security into a single, functional dimension of confidence. This adaptability positions the FLCS as the first truly pluricentric instrument in the field, one capable of capturing what might be called FLC's "contextual choreography." This finding extends Liu's (2024) work into World Englishes territory, providing empirical evidence that our measurement tools must be as flexible and dynamic as the global use of English itself.

From a pedagogical perspective, the emergence of the Global Confidence Model offers clear guidance for educators in international higher education. The dominance of the Pragmatic Confidence factor suggests that assessment practices should shift away from native-centric rubrics focused on accuracy and toward criteria based on intelligibility, communicative effectiveness, and task achievement. To foster the crucial Linguistic Ownership, instruction should explicitly address the history and reality of Global Englishes, helping students to deconstruct the "native speaker ghost" and develop pride and a sense of belonging in their own unique voices as multilingual users of English. As Jenkins (2015) argued, the ELF classroom must be fundamentally different from the EFL classroom; our model provides an evidence-based framework for enacting that transformation.

While the diversity of our sample strengthens the findings, we acknowledge that the data were collected from a single institution, which may limit generalizability. Future research should therefore aim to validate this two-factor Global Confidence Model in other expanding circle contexts to confirm its stability. Furthermore, while our quantitative data revealed the merged

structure of Pragmatic Confidence, mixed-methods research incorporating qualitative interviews could provide invaluable insight into the lived experiences behind this phenomenon, exploring precisely how and why learners in ELF settings merge their sense of competence and security. Finally, longitudinal studies are needed to track how students' confidence structures evolve over time with increased exposure to multicultural ELF environments.

In conclusion, this study makes a vital contribution by validating the FLCS as an instrument capable of more than was initially conceived. It does not merely measure confidence; it captures how confidence reorganizes itself to meet the communicative and ideological demands of its environment. By revealing the adaptable nature of FLC, this research moves the field beyond static measurement and toward a more nuanced understanding of how language learners develop the self-assurance needed to claim their rightful place in a world where English belongs to everyone who uses it.

REFERENCES

- Al-Hoorie, Ali H., Hiver, Phil., Kim, Tae-Young, & De Costa, Peter. 2021. *The L2 Motivational Self System: A meta-analysis of 124 studies*. Routledge.
- Bandura, Albert. 1997. *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. W. H. Freeman.
- Bolton, Kingsley. 2018. World Englishes: Current trends and future directions. *Asian Englishes*, 20(1), 2-19.
- Byrne, Barbara M. 2012. *Structural equation modeling with Mplus: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*. Routledge.
- Byrne, Barbara M. 2016. *Structural equation modeling with AMOS: Basic concepts, applications, and programming* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Canagarajah, Suresh. 2014. In search of a new paradigm for teaching English as an international language. *TESOL Journal*, 5(4), 767-785. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesj.166>
- Chen, Fang Fang. 2007. Sensitivity of goodness of fit indexes to lack of measurement invariance. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 14(3), 464–504. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705510701301834>
- Cheung, Gordon W., & Rensvold, Roger. B. 2002. Evaluating goodness-of-fit indexes for testing measurement invariance. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 9(2), 233–255. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15328007SEM0902_5

- Clément, Richard. 1980. Ethnicity, contact and communicative competence in a second language. In H. Giles, W. P. Robinson, & P. M. Smith (Eds.), *Language: Social psychological perspectives* (pp. 147-154). Pergamon Press.
- Clément, Richard., Dörnyei, Zoltán., & Noels, Kimberley A. 1994. Motivation, self-confidence, and group cohesion in the foreign language classroom. *Language Learning*, 44(3), 417-448.
- Darvin, Ron., & Norton, Bonny. 2015. Identity and a model of investment in language learning. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 35, 36-56.
- Dewaele, Jean-Marc. 2018. Why the dichotomy 'L1 versus LX user' is better than 'native versus non-native speaker'. *Applied Linguistics*, 39(2), 236-240. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amw055>
- Dewaele, Jean-Marc., & MacIntyre, Peter D. 2019. The predictive power of sociobiographical and task-related variables on Foreign Language Enjoyment and Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(4), 633–660.
- Dewey, Martin. 2007. English as a lingua franca: A new variety in the new expanding circle? In Jim Cummins & Chris Davison (Eds.), *International handbook of English language teaching* (Vol. 1, pp. 361-374). Springer.
- Dörnyei, Zoltán., & Taguchi, Tatsuya. 2010. *Questionnaires in second language research: Construction, administration, and processing* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Galloway, Nicola., & Rose, Heath. 2015. *Introducing Global Englishes*. Routledge.
- Gao, Xuesong., & Zhang, Lawrence Jun. 2020. Teacher agency and identity in language education: A narrative inquiry from a complexity perspective. *System*, 91, 102251.
- Gardner, Robert C., & MacIntyre, Peter D. 1993. A student's contributions to second-language learning. Part II: Affective variables. *Language Teaching*, 26(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444800000045>
- Gordani, Yahya., Arabani, Arash Saharkhiz, & Moghtader, Iman Javadzadeh. 2021. Communication anxiety and self-confidence among learners of English as a foreign language: The role of learning cooperatively. *Global Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 11(4), 257–270. <https://doi.org/10.18844/gjflt.v11i4.6114>

- Guo, Yi. 2024. The effect of foreign language enjoyment on students' foreign language learning. *Lecture Notes in Education Psychology and Public Media*, 70(1), 184–189. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2753-7048/70/20241021>
- Hambleton, Ronald K., Merenda, Peter F., & Spielberger, Charles D. (Eds.). 2005. *Adapting educational and psychological tests for cross-cultural assessment*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Horwitz, Elaine K., Horwitz, Michael B., & Cope, Joann. 1986. Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125-132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1986.tb05256.x>
- Hu, Li-tze, & Bentler, Peter M. 1999. Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 6(1), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- International Test Commission. 2017. *The ITC guidelines for translating and adapting tests* (2nd ed.). Author.
- Jenkins, Jennifer. 2000. *The phonology of English as an international language*. Oxford University Press.
- Jenkins, Jennifer. 2006. Current perspectives on teaching World Englishes and English as a Lingua Franca. *TESOL Quarterly*, 40(1), 157-181.
- Jenkins, Jennifer. 2007. *English as a Lingua Franca: Attitude and Identity*. Oxford University Press.
- Jenkins, Jennifer. 2015. *Global Englishes: A resource book for students* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Kachru, Braj B. 1985. Standards, codification and sociolinguistic realism: The English language in the outer circle. In R. Quirk & H. G. Widdowson (Eds.), *English in the world: Teaching and learning the language and literatures* (pp. 11-30). Cambridge University Press.
- Kirkpatrick, A. 2007. *World Englishes: Implications for international communication and English language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kline, Rex B. 2016. *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (4th ed.). Guilford Press.

- Liu, Guangxiang Leon. 2024. Revisiting and measuring foreign language confidence from a World Englishes perspective: Scale development and validation. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 35(1), 291–307. Portico. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijal.12618>
- MacIntyre, Peter D., Clément, Richard., Dörnyei, Zoltán, & Noels, Kimberley A. 1998. Conceptualizing willingness to communicate in a L2: A situational model of L2 confidence and affiliation. *The Modern Language Journal*, 82(4), 545-562. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1998.tb05543.x>
- McKay, Sandra L. 2002. *Teaching English as an international language: Rethinking goals and approaches*. Oxford University Press.
- Norton, Bonny. 2000. *Identity and language learning: Gender, ethnicity and educational change*. Longman.
- Oktaria, Putrika. 2023. The correlation between self-confidence and English speaking achievement of the secondary school students. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Dan Menengah*, 1(2), 54–67. <https://doi.org/10.69743/edumedia.v1i2.18>
- Ortega, Lourdes. 2019. SLA and the study of equitable multilingualism. *The Modern Language Journal*, 103(1), 23-38. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12525>
- Park, Joseph Sung-Yul., & Wee, Lionel. 2012. *Markets of English: Linguistic capital and language policy in a globalizing world*. Routledge.
- Rajagopalan, Kanavillil. 2004. The concept of 'World English' and its implications for ELT. *ELT Journal*, 58(2), 111-117. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/58.2.111>
- Seidlhofer, Barbara. 2011. *Understanding English as a Lingua Franca*. Oxford University Press.
- Sifakis, Nicos C. 2014. ELF awareness as an opportunity for change: A transformative perspective for ESOL teacher education. *Journal of English as a Lingua Franca*, 3(2), 317-335. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jelf-2014-0019>
- Teimouri, Yasser., Goetze, Julia, & Plonsky, Luke. 2019. Second language anxiety and achievement: A meta-analysis. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 41(2), 363-387. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263118000311>

- Tupas, Ruanni. 2015. Inequalities of multilingualism: Challenges to mother tongue-based multilingual education. *Language and Education*, 29(2), 112-124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2014.977295>
- Van de Vijver, Fons J. R., & Leung, Kwok. 1997. *Methods and data analysis for cross-cultural research*. Sage Publications.
- Van de Vijver, Fons J. R., & Leung, Kwok. 2021. Methods and data analysis for cross-cultural research. In D. Matsumoto & F. J. R. Van de Vijver (Eds.), *Cross-cultural research methods in psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 30–63). Cambridge University Press.
- Vandenberg, Robert J., & Lance, Charles E. 2000. A review and synthesis of the measurement invariance literature: Suggestions, practices, and recommendations for organizational research. *Organizational Research Methods*, 3(1), 4-70.
- Zhang, Qinghe., Song, Yan, & Zhao, Chen. 2023. *Foreign language enjoyment and willingness to communicate: The mediating role of communication confidence and motivation*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4539192>
- Zhang, Xian. 2019. Foreign language anxiety and foreign language performance: A meta-analysis. *The Modern Language Journal*, 103(4), 763-781. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12590>
- Zhou, Tianyu, & Kuok, Ucheng. 2024. The emotional impact of L1 learning confidence on L2 learning: A case of a study of translation majors in Guangxi Universities. *International Journal of English Language Studies*, 6(4), 16–24. <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijels.2024.6.4.4>